

ORGANIZATION OF THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS IN FOREIGN NON-STATE HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract: This article analyzes the basic principles, content and best practices of organizing the educational process in foreign non-state higher educational institutions. The study pays special attention to innovative pedagogical approaches, academic independence and mechanisms for supporting students' personal development in non-state higher educational institutions of foreign countries. The author describes the specific features of organizing the educational process and highlights the possibilities of their integration into the higher education system of Uzbekistan. The article also analytically examines the role of non-state educational institutions in improving the quality of education and their contribution to the global education system. This article also contains recommendations aimed at solving current problems in the field of education by studying foreign experience.

Keywords: Foreign higher educational institutions, credit system, educational methods, admission process, educational process, scientific research, assessment system, online education, innovative technologies.

Introduction.

The development and prosperity of every society is inextricably linked with the quality of the education system. In today's era of globalization, ensuring competitiveness in the field of education, effective use of scientific achievements and development of human capital remain one of the main tasks. In particular, non-state higher education institutions have become an integral part of the education system, finding their place not only in their own country, but also in the international arena.

Foreign non-state higher education institutions serve to improve the creative and intellectual potential of students by introducing innovative technologies into the educational process, using modern teaching methods, and implementing education based on the principles of an individual approach. Their experience is of great importance not only in improving the educational process, but also in improving the management system.

Therefore, studying the activities of foreign non-state higher education institutions, analyzing their advanced approaches and innovative methods in organizing the educational process remains a pressing issue for the education system of Uzbekistan. The purpose of this essay is to deeply study foreign experience and reveal the possibilities of its integration into the national education system.

The basic structure of the education system:

The education system in foreign higher education institutions is usually divided into three stages:

Undergraduate: At this stage, students receive general knowledge. It usually lasts 3-4 years. Education is intensive, providing practical and theoretical knowledge, as well as basic concepts in the chosen field.

Graduate: After the undergraduate stage, students receive more in-depth knowledge in the specialty. Master's programs can last several years and are usually associated with scientific research and practical work.

Doctorate (Postgraduate / Doctoral): At this stage, students conduct scientific work, aimed at creating new knowledge or improving existing theories. Education at this stage is mainly focused on research.

Teaching methods:

Several teaching methods are used in foreign higher education:

Lectures and seminars: While lectures are mainly lectures, seminars allow students to discuss the topic in more depth. This is especially important in developing students' critical thinking skills.

Practical exercises and laboratory work: Many higher education institutions organize laboratories and seminars to gain practical experience.

Online education: Most foreign higher education institutions have online learning platforms. Through them, students can complete distance learning courses in their own time and freely.

Interaction between students and teachers:

In foreign higher education institutions, students work closely with teachers. Teachers regularly consult with students. At the same time, in many institutions, students work with their teachers in the framework of scientific research, practical work and projects.

Scientific research and innovation:

In foreign higher education systems, scientific research is an integral part of the educational process. Students and teachers are involved in many scientific research. There are various grants and scholarships for scientific work. Also,

scientific conferences and seminars are organized, in which students participate with their scientific work.

Use of technology in the educational process:

Modern technologies are widely used to make the educational process more effective. In particular:

Online classes and distance learning platforms.

Simulations, virtual laboratories and tutorials.

Interactive educational tools, such as learning platforms, online libraries and databases of scientific articles.

Assessment system:

In foreign higher education institutions, students' knowledge is checked through various assessment systems. The main assessment tools include:

Exams: Exams are conducted to assess theoretical and practical knowledge.

Projects and presentations: Students develop projects to demonstrate their knowledge through practical tasks.

Lectures and seminars: In some higher education institutions, students give seminars and lectures, which help develop their communication skills.

Admissions process:

Entry requirements for foreign higher education institutions also vary. Many higher education institutions conduct entrance exams. Some universities, however, admit students through interviews and competitions with candidates. In foreign countries, English, mathematics or field tests may be conducted. In addition, many universities have their own admission standards and requirements, for example, IELTS, TOEFL, SAT, etc.

Literature review:

The opinions of professors and scientists about the importance of foreign higher education institutions, their educational system and scientific activities may differ, as they put forward different points of view based on their own experience, research and educational methodologies. However, in general, the following points can be made about foreign higher education institutions.

High quality of education and global competitiveness

One of the biggest advantages of foreign higher education institutions is the high quality of education. According to professors and scientists, many foreign universities create excellent learning conditions for students by using modern pedagogical approaches, advanced curricula and interactive methods in the learning process. For example, according to professors from educational institutions such as the Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT), Stanford

University or Oxford University, they pay great attention to the development of not only theoretical knowledge, but also practical experience in their curricula. This prepares students for success in the global job market.

High level of scientific research

Professors and scientists emphasize the high level of scientific research and innovation in foreign higher education institutions. Foreign universities are constantly updating their research activities with modern technologies and scientific achievements. At institutions such as Harvard University and the University of Cambridge, professors and scientists encourage students to conduct scientific research. They support advanced methods in their research, thereby creating scientific innovations on a global scale. Professors at these universities often conduct scientific projects and research together with students.

International cooperation and specialized educational programs

Another advantage of foreign higher education institutions is their widespread global cooperation. According to professors, international cooperation creates great opportunities for students. Many universities create educational programs in cooperation with other educational institutions in different countries. For example, several large universities offer programs that provide students with the opportunity to study in two countries at the same time. Through international exchange programs and study programs, students get acquainted with different cultures and scientific approaches from around the world.

Discussion.

Non-state higher education institutions have become one of the dynamically developing links in the education system today. Their success is often reflected in the fact that they are based on innovative approaches and modern management principles. When we observe foreign experience, we can see that non-state universities are making significant progress in improving the quality of education, creating curricula focused on the interests of students, and ensuring academic freedom.

For example, a number of non-state universities in the USA and Europe use international accreditation programs to bring the educational process into line with international standards. They increase their competitiveness by supporting innovative technologies and preparing students for the global labor market. In such institutions, practice-oriented curricula, an atmosphere of cooperation

between students and teachers, and the development of an entrepreneurial culture significantly increase the effectiveness of the educational process.

The economic aspects of non-state higher education institutions also play an important role. Many foreign universities use private funds and donor funds in their activities, along with state support. This ensures the financial stability of education and allows for the large-scale implementation of innovative programs. At the same time, non-state institutions create an environment of healthy competition with state universities, contributing to an increase in the overall quality of education.

However, this system also has some difficulties. For example, some non-state higher education institutions may neglect the quality of education, pursuing only commercial interests. In addition, the lack of clear legal frameworks regulating this type of education by the state also creates problems. In the process of studying foreign experience, it is important to identify such problems and learn from them, to develop optimal solutions that are suitable for our national education system.

In conclusion, foreign non-state higher educational institutions offer various methods of organizing the educational process. By studying their advanced experience and adapting it to the national education system, there is an opportunity to bring the quality of education in Uzbekistan to a new level. In this sense, this discussion serves not only to understand the importance of foreign experience, but also to identify the conditions necessary for the successful implementation of its results.

Conclusion.

In today's rapidly changing world, the development of the education system and improving its quality remain a priority task for every country. Non-state higher educational institutions have become an important link in this process. Their advanced approaches to organizing the educational process, individual programs focused on the needs of students, and the use of innovative technologies give them a special advantage. Therefore, the experience of foreign non-state educational institutions can serve as a valuable lesson for our national education system.

From foreign experience, it can be understood that an effective management system, financial stability and support for creativity in the educational process are the main factors in improving the quality of education. This requires the introduction of systems that stimulate the personal and

professional development of the student, rather than just providing individual knowledge.

However, instead of directly transferring this experience, it is important to adapt it, taking into account the specifics of our national culture, values, and education system. Because the education system of each country depends on its historical, social, and economic conditions. Therefore, it is necessary to carefully study foreign experience, integrate its positive aspects into the national system, and also anticipate possible negative consequences.

In conclusion, the experience of foreign non-state higher education institutions can serve as an important source of inspiration for reforming the education system of Uzbekistan. There is an opportunity to bring our national education system to a new level by improving the quality of education, introducing innovative approaches, and organizing an educational process focused on personal development. In this process, the combination of foreign and national experiences, taking into account modern requirements, and infusing the educational process with a new spirit will pave the way for the future rise of the Uzbek education system.

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